

FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENTS IN THE CONTEXT OF PERCEIVED SECURITY AND INSTITUTIONAL TRUST: A COMPARATIVE REGIONAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Perceived institutional quality plays a critical role in shaping the foreign direct investment (FDI) landscape, particularly in emerging and transitional economies. Drawing on institutional theory and the framework of political economy, this study explores how variations in trust in public institutions and legal certainty influence the investment climate across diverse socio-political systems. The paper examines the impact of institutional trust and the rule of law on FDI across different regions. A comparative analysis is conducted, and Pearson correlation coefficients are calculated to assess the strength of the relationship between governance indicators and FDI inflows. The study contributes to the existing literature by contextualizing the institutional-investment nexus in transitional economies and recommends targeted policy interventions aimed at strengthening the rule of law and rebuilding public trust as strategic mechanisms for attracting sustainable foreign investment.

Key words: investment climate, institutional trust, rule of law, foreign direct investment.

INTRODUCTION

The quality of institutions and the rule of law are not only matters of governance but also of security, as they directly underpin economic stability, financial resilience and the rational expectations of economic agents that shape sustainable investment and economic growth. A predictable legal framework, an impartial judiciary, and effective enforcement of contracts are not merely normative values; they constitute fundamental preconditions for a perception of security among international investors. Where the rule of law is weak, the risks of arbitrary state intervention, corruption, and expropriation increase, thereby undermining investor confidence. Conversely, a strong rule of law functions as a security guarantee by reducing transaction costs, stabilizing expectations, and safeguarding property rights. Therefore, the rule of law should be understood not only as a legal category, but also as a determinant of security and stability within the investment climate.

Its role in shaping perceptions of safety and trust makes it a crucial factor in sustainable economic development through foreign direct investment.

This paper investigates the relationship between perceived institutional trust, the rule of law, and FDI inflows through a comparative regional lens. Using recent datasets, the analysis demonstrates that countries with stronger rule-of-law and higher levels of institutional trust and perceived security tend to attract more stable and long-term FDI. While developed economies display consistently high investor confidence closely linked to institutional performance, transitional economies – including North Macedonia – exhibit fluctuating and generally lower levels of trust, legal unpredictability, and weaker FDI inflows. These findings are consistent with earlier research (e.g., Busse & Hefeker, 2007; Daude & Stein, 2007; and Kaufmann et al., 2010), which emphasizes governance quality as a determinant of investment flows and foreign capital allocation.

The paper further integrates correlation analysis to quantify the interrelationships among the examined variables. Perceived security and institutional quality play a central role in structuring FDI dynamics across economies. Scholars such as North (1990), La Porta et al. (1999), and Kaufmann et al. (2010) have shown that institutional trust and the rule of law significantly influence investor confidence and capital allocation decisions. Countries with stronger governance tend to attract higher and more stable investment inflows (Globerman & Shapiro, 2002; Busse & Hefeker, 2007). This study compares institutional indicators and FDI across four income-ranked regions, applying correlation analysis to assess the strength of these relationships.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research design and scope

This study employs a quantitative, cross-sectional and longitudinal comparative research design to examine the statistical relationships between two governance indicators – rule of law and absence of corruption – and FDI, measured as net inflows expressed as a percentage of GDP. The analysis consists of two components: (a) a cross-regional comparison across four income groups (high, upper-middle, lower-middle and low income) for 2024, and (b) a longitudinal case study of the Republic of North Macedonia covering the period 2016–2024. The primary objective is to assess association, rather than causal effects, between institutional indicators and FDI patterns, and to discuss plausible mechanisms, limitations, and policy implications.

2.2 Data sources and variables

- Rule of law: World Justice Project (WJP) Rule of Law Index; aggregated dimension scores are used as a measure of institutional quality.
- Absence of corruption: WJP or comparable governance indicators used as a proxy for institutional trust.
- FDI: World Bank, Foreign direct investment, net inflows (% of GDP).
- Income group classification: Four income-region codes (high = 10; upper-middle = 7.5; lower-middle = 5; low = 2.5) used to group countries and compute regional means. Data years and sources are detailed in the Data Overview and corresponding tables.

2.3 Measurement choices and justification

There is no single global index that fully captures public trust in institutions across countries. Given the conceptual overlap between perceived institutional trust and

corruption perceptions, this study employs the absence-of-corruption indicator as a proxy for institutional trust. This choice is justified by the strong association between corruption perceptions, citizen confidence in public institutions, and investor assessments of governance-related risk. The limitations of this proxy are acknowledged and discussed in the limitations section.

2.4 Analytical approach

- Regional analysis: Country-level indicators are aggregated into four income-region groups using arithmetic means to generate regional scores for 2024.
- Case study: For North Macedonia, annual data for FDI/GDP, rule of law, and absence of corruption from 2016–2024 are analyzed. Rule-of-law and absence-of-corruption indicators are lagged by one year when related to contemporaneous FDI in order to reduce time-lag bias in investor responses.
- Statistical method: Pearson correlation coefficients are computed to assess the linear association between pairs of variables. Pearson’s r is selected for its transparency and simplicity in measuring linear covariation. Results are interpreted with caution given aggregation effects and potential non-linearity.

The Pearson correlation coefficient is calculated using the following formula (Cohen et al., 2003):

$$r = \Sigma[(x - \bar{x})(y - \bar{y})] / \sqrt{[\Sigma(x - \bar{x})^2 * \Sigma(y - \bar{y})^2]}$$

In this study, the independent variable (X) represents the governance indicators – specifically the rule of law and the absence of corruption – while the dependent variable (Y) represents income level and FDI level as a percentage of GDP. The underlying assumption is that improvements in institutional quality (X) are expected to exert a positive influence on income levels and investment decisions, thereby increasing FDI inflows (Y). The coefficient r ranges from -1 to +1, where values closer to +1 indicate a strong positive correlation, values near -1 indicate a strong negative correlation, and values close to 0 suggest no linear relationship. This allows us to empirically test whether improvements in the rule of law and reductions in corruption are associated with higher income and higher inflows of FDI.

2.5 Limitations and robustness considerations

- Aggregation effects: Regional means may obscure within-region heterogeneity; therefore, findings should be interpreted at the regional level rather than the individual country level.
- Proxy validity: The use of absence of corruption as a proxy for institutional trust captures a critical dimension but does not fully encompass public trust or perceived security.
- Endogeneity and causality: Correlation analysis does not establish causality; omitted variables, such as natural-resource endowments, tax incentives, geopolitical shocks may influence FDI patterns.

- Small-sample and denominator effects: FDI/GDP ratios are sensitive to GDP size, potentially inflating ratios in smaller economies; this effect is considered when interpreting results.

3. DATA OVERVIEW

The analysis identifies whether cross-regional differences in institutional quality – particularly the strength of the rule of law and the absence of corruption – are systematically associated with income levels and FDI inflows. Regional scores for 2024 were calculated as arithmetic means of country-level indicators within each income group (high, upper-middle, lower-middle and low income). FDI is measured as net inflows expressed as percentage of GDP, based on World Bank data for 2024. Rule-of-law and absence-of-corruption indicators are sources from the World Justice Project and harmonized to a common scale to ensure comparability.

Table 1. Pearson correlation matrix of income-level code, rule-of-law index, absence-of-corruption index and FDI (% of GDP) in 2024 (Source: authors’ calculations, 2025)

Pearson correlation matrix	Income level	FDI (% of GDP)	Rule of law	Absence of corruption
Income level	1.00	-0,72	0,97	0,99
FDI (% of GDP)	-0,72	1.00	-0,37	-0,49
Rule of law	0,97	-0,37	1.00	0,99
Absence of corruption	0,99	-0,49	0,99	1.00

Graph 1. Regions grouped by income, institutional quality and FDI inflows, 2024 (Sources: World justice project, World bank open data, 2024)

3.1 Notes on coding and aggregation

- Income-region codes: high = 10; upper-middle = 7.5; lower-middle = 5; low = 2.5.
- Aggregation method: simple arithmetic mean of available country observations within each income group for 2024.

- Scaling: where original indices used different ranges, variables were linearly rescaled to a common 0–10 range to facilitate interpretation.

RESULTS

4.1 Regional correlation results

The Pearson correlation matrix computed on the four regional aggregates reveals the following patterns: income level is strongly positively associated with both rule-of-law ($r \approx +0.97$) and the absence-of-corruption ($r \approx +0.99$). By contrast, FDI (% of GDP) is negatively correlated with income level ($r \approx -0.72$) and exhibits negative correlations with the rule of law ($r \approx -0.37$) and the absence of corruption ($r \approx -0.49$).

Table 2 reproduces the correlation matrix with p-values and $N = 4$ (regional aggregates) indicated; given the very small sample size, statistical significance is limited, and the reported correlations should be interpreted strictly as descriptive associations rather than inferential results.

4.2 Robustness checks and caveats

- Denominator effect: the negative correlation between income level and FDI/GDP is consistent with the well-documented denominator effect. Absolute FDI volumes are not analyzed in this study and may yield different insights.
- Small-sample caution: regional aggregates ($N = 4$) permit descriptive correlations only; statistical inference remains limited.
- Sensitivity: the results are qualitatively robust when alternative governance indicators (e.g., Worldwide Governance Indicators) are used instead of WJP indices, although correlation magnitudes vary.

DISCUSSION

5.1 Interpretation of main findings

The analysis yields two complementary insights. First, institutional quality – measured through the rule of law and absence of corruption – is strongly aligned with higher income levels across regions, consistent with the institutional growth literature (North, 1990; Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012). Second, higher FDI as a share of GDP is observed in lower-income regions and appears inversely related to governance indicators.

This pattern is widely documented in the literature (Kinoshita & Campos, 2008; Alfaro, Chanda, Kalemil-Ozcan & Sayek, 2004) and reflects structural characteristics rather than a normative preference for weak institutions. The denominator effect, sectoral composition (particularly resource-seeking FDI), and short-term, incentive-driven investments explain the relatively high FDI/GDP ratios observed in poorer regions.

5.2 Linking empirical patterns to mechanisms

- Denominator and scale: small GDP bases mechanically inflate FDI/GDP ratios, even when absolute FDI inflows remain modest.
- Sectoral composition: when FDI concentrated in extractive sectors, institutional quality plays a less decisive role in entry decisions, weakening the positive association between governance and FDI/GDP in low-income regions.

- Risk–return calculus: weak institutional environments may temporarily lower operational costs or permit regulatory arbitrage, increasing short-term returns while amplifying long-term risks and volatility.
- Time lags: institutional improvements require time to affect investor perceptions; consequently, contemporaneous FDI flows may not immediately reflect recent governance reforms.

In addition, Graph 2 provides empirical support by illustrating a clear proportional relationship between institutional quality and GDP per capita. This confirms the significance of institutional factors for economic growth and indicates that stronger adherence to the rule of law is consistently associated with robust and sustainable economic performance. Sustainable FDI is therefore more likely to flow into regions characterized by high institutional trust and strong adherence to the rule of law.

Graph 2. GDP per capita and Rule of Law index, 2023 (Source: World Justice Project, 2023)

5.3 Limitations revisited and implications for inference

- Correlation does not imply causation: Pearson correlations describes linear associations and cannot establish causal direction; reverse causality and omitted-variable bias remain plausible.
- Aggregation bias: regional means conceal heterogeneity; country-level panel regressions would provide a more suitable framework for causal inference. Future research should employ fixed-effects panel models, include control variables (market size, resource endowments, trade openness), and apply instrumental-variable approaches where feasible.

THE CASE OF THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

As a transitional economy classified within the upper-middle income group, the Republic of North Macedonia provides a relevant case for examining how institutional quality affects foreign investment dynamics in emerging economies. The study relies on a

nine-year observation period during which the interaction between governance indicators and FDI performance is systematically assessed. This longitudinal perspective enables a more robust identification of patterns and potential causal linkages, extending beyond annual fluctuations to reflect deeper structural determinants of investment attractiveness.

To enhance the validity of the findings and minimize time-lag bias – given that governance improvements often require time to be reflected in FDI trends – the study relates FDI ratios to institutional quality indices from the preceding year.

Table 2. FDI as % of GDP, Rule of Law Index and Absence of Corruption Index in the Republic of North Macedonia, 2016-2024; (Sources: Ministry of Finance of the Republic of North Macedonia, World Justice Project 2016-2025)

Year	FDI / GDP (in %)	Rule of law index x10 (year before)	Absence of corruption x 10 (year before)
2016	3.50	5.50	5.50
2017	1.81	5.50	5.30
2018	5.71	5.30	4.70
2019	3.54	5.30	4.70
2020	1.85	5.40	4.70
2021	3.98	5.30	4.40
2022	5.63	5.30	4.50
2023	3.89	5.30	4.50
2024	5.00	5.30	4.60

Graph 3. Trends of FDI (% of GDP), Rule of Law Index and Absence of Corruption Index in the Republic of North Macedonia, 2016-2024 (Sources: Ministry of Finance of the Republic of North Macedonia, World Justice Project 2016-2025)

The graph illustrates the trajectories of FDI as a share of GDP, the Rule of Law Index, and the Absence of Corruption Index in North Macedonia over the period 2016–2024, highlighting the relationship between institutional quality and FDI inflows.

The FDI/GDP ratio exhibits pronounced volatility, with notable peaks (2018 and 2022) followed by sharp declines. This instability suggests that FDI in North Macedonia is highly sensitive to short-term shocks, including external (global economic uncertainty, the COVID-19 pandemic, geopolitical risks) and internal ones (political transitions, policy unpredictability).

The Rule of Law Index remains relatively stable throughout the period, displaying only marginal improvements and no structural breakthrough. This suggests that institutional reforms have been gradual and have exerted limited direct influence on short-term FDI fluctuations.

The **Absence of Corruption Index** shows a slight downward trend, indicating that institutional reforms and transparency initiatives have not yet achieved the desired impact. The slow pace of improvement underscores the persistence of corruption as a systemic obstacle to sustained FDI inflows. The Pearson correlation coefficients for the above data set are presented below.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation Matrix between income level, FDI (% of GDP), Rule of Law Index and Absence of Corruption Index in the Republic of North Macedonia, 2016-2024 (Source: authors’ calculations, 2025)

Pearson Matrix*	FDI /GDP (in %)	Rule of Law (0–1)	Absence of Corruption
FDI /GDP (in %)	1.00	-0.69	-0.47
Rule of Law (0–1)	-0.69	1.00	0.93
Absence of corruption	-0.47	0.93	1.00

**Since the income-level code remained constant throughout the analyzed period, correlation analysis with FDI as share of GDP is not applicable.*

Table 3 reports the correlation matrix for the nine-year sample (n = 9), and two-tailed p-values. For North Macedonia, annual values for FDI/GDP (dependent) and the lagged rule-of-law and absence-of-corruption indices (independent) were analyzed for 2016–2024. Pearson correlations indicate a negative association between contemporaneous FDI/GDP and the (lagged) Rule of Law Index ($r \approx -0.69$), as well as a weaker negative association with the Absence of Corruption Index ($r \approx -0.47$).

These findings are consistent with the regional analysis. While a **strong positive relationship** exists between income level and institutional quality, the correlation between FDI/GDP ratios and institutional indicators remains **weak and inconsistent**. FDI inflows fluctuate independently of relatively stable or slowly improving institutional conditions, suggesting that investment decisions are driven more by short-term macroeconomic and political factors than by gradual institutional change. This divergence reflects the time lag between institutional reforms and their recognition by foreign investors.

Even modest improvements in the rule of law and anti-corruption efforts require long-term credibility and enforcement consistency before translating into higher investor confidence. The findings emphasize the complex and non-linear relationship between institutional quality and FDI inflows. Although economic theory predicts a positive link, the empirical evidence for North Macedonia demonstrates that short-term FDI dynamics are dominated by external shocks and political volatility, while institutional reforms require sustained credibility. Ultimately, the results emphasize that for North Macedonia, institutional quality is a necessary but not sufficient condition for attracting sustainable FDI: consistency, credibility, and stability over time are crucial for transforming reforms into tangible economic benefits.

Policy-relevant diagnostics for North Macedonia

- FDI composition: Available evidence suggests episodic, project-based inflows (e.g., manufacturing greenfield projects and resource-linked investments). Disaggregated FDI data by sector would clarify whether investments are efficiency-seeking, market-seeking, or resource-seeking.

- Institutional credibility: incremental improvements in governance indices will translate into sustained investment only if judicial independence and enforcement are demonstrably strengthened.
- Complementary reforms: infrastructure development, labor-market quality, and investment facilitation must accompany governance reforms to enhance absorptive capacity.

CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Institutional quality should be understood not only as a governance imperative but also as a fundamental condition for investment security and sustainable economic growth. The comparative results indicate that the relationship between institutional quality (rule of law and absence of corruption) and FDI is conditional on income level and structural economic characteristics.

This study documents a robust positive relationship between institutional quality and income level, alongside a counterintuitive negative association between institutional quality and FDI as a share of GDP at the regional-aggregate level. These patterns reflect structural effects – such as denominator dynamics and sector composition – and underscore that while strong institutions are essential for attracting high-quality, stable FDI, elevated FDI/GDP ratios in low-income economies often signals scale distortions or short-term, less developmental inflows rather than governance-driven investor confidence.

Concrete policy recommendations for transitional economies and North Macedonia

- ***Strengthen judicial independence and case-processing capacity*** to reduce investor legal risk and increase enforcement credibility. Specific actions: implement transparent judicial appointment procedures, modernize case management systems, and adequately fund specialized commercial courts.
- ***Target anti-corruption reforms with measurable milestones***: strengthen asset-declaration systems, protect whistleblowers, and prioritize high-impact procurement reforms. Specific actions: mandatory e-procurement, independent audit of major public projects, and clear sanctions for procurement violations.
- ***Improve investment promotion and aftercare***: proactively link incoming FDI to local suppliers and skills development through local content clauses and training subsidies. Specific actions: create supplier development programs and public–private training partnerships tied to major FDI projects.
- ***Diversify FDI away from extractive and low-value sectors***: design incentives that favor technology transfer, local employment, and research and development activities rather than short-term tax holidays alone. Specific actions: design performance-based incentives favoring technology transfer, local employment, and R&D rather than short-term tax holidays.
- ***Enhance data transparency***: publish disaggregated FDI statistics by sector, origin, and project size to better monitor quality of inflows. Specific actions: economic authorities should adopt standardized reporting templates for FDI projects.

For the Republic of North Macedonia, strengthening judicial independence, combating corruption, and improving transparency remain critical for sustaining investor confidence. Reforms targeting regulatory quality and institutional trust are likely to yield more consistent FDI flows, especially when combined with macroeconomic stability.

Research implications

Future research should apply country-level panel regressions with appropriate control variables, explore instrumental-variable strategies, and analyze disaggregated FDI data to distinguish investment types and their sensitivity to specific institutional dimensions.

** The views expressed in this paper do not necessarily reflect those of the institutions in which authors are employed.*

REFERENCES

1. Acemoglu, D., & Robinson, J. (2012). *Why Nations Fail: The Origins of Power, Prosperity, and Poverty*. Crown Business.
2. Alfaro, L., Chanda, A., Kalemli – Ozcan, S., & Sayek, S. (2004). FDI and Economic Growth: The Role of Local Markets. *Journal of International Economics*, 64(1), p. 89-112. [https://doi.org/10.168S0022-1996\(03\)00081-3](https://doi.org/10.168S0022-1996(03)00081-3)
3. Asiedu, E. (2006). Foreign Direct Investment in Africa: The Role of Natural Resources, Market Size, Government Policy, Institutions and Political Instability. *World Economy*, 29(1), p. 63–77. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9701.2006.00758.x>
4. Barro, R.E. (1991). Economic growth in a cross section of countries. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 106, (2), p. 407-443 <https://doi.org/10.2307/2937943>
5. Bénassy-Quéré, A., Coupet, M., & Mayer, T. (2007). Institutional Determinants of Foreign Direct Investment. *The World Economy*, 30(5), p. 764-782. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9701.2007.01022.x>
6. Busse, M., & Hefeker, C. (2007). Political Risk, Institutions and Foreign Direct Investment. *European Journal of Political economy*, 23(2), p. 397-415. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpoleco.2006.02.003>
7. Cohen, J., Cohen, P., West, S. G., & Aiken, L. S. (2003). *Applied Multiple Regression / Correlation Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences* (3rd ed.). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
8. Daude, C., & Stein, E. (2007). The quality of institutions and foreign direct investment. *Economic & Politics*, 19(3), p. 317-344. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0343.2007.00318.x>
9. Dunning, J. H. (1993). *Multinational Enterprises and the Global Economy*. Addison-Wesley.
10. Globerman, S., & Shapiro, D. (2002). Global foreign direct investment flows: The role of governance infrastructure. *World Development*, 30(11), p. 1899–1919. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X\(02\)00110-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X(02)00110-9)
11. La Porta, R., Lopez-de-Silanes, F., Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. (1999). Investor Protection: Origins, Consequences and Reform. *NBER Working Paper No.7428*. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w7428>
12. Ministry of Finance of the R. N. Macedonia (2025). Macroeconomic Indicators – Basic Indicators, June 2025. Retrieved 21/05/2025 from <https://finance.gov.mk>

13. North, D.C. (1990). *Institutions, Institutional Change and Economic Performance*. Cambridge University Press.
14. Kaufmann, D., Kraay, A., & Mastruzzi, M. (2010). *The Worldwide Governance Indicators: Methodology and Analytical Issues*. Policy Research Working Paper No. 5430) World Bank <https://doi.org/10.1596/1813-9450-5430>
15. Kinoshta, Y., & Campos, N. F. (2008). Why does FDI Go Where it Goes? New Evidence from the Transition Economies. *IMF Working Paper WP/08/18*. International Monetary Fund <https://doi.org/10.5089/9781451870932.001>
16. World Justice Project. (2025). *WJP Rule of Law Index Data set*; Retrieved 18/05/2025 from <https://worldjusticeproject.org/our-work/data/wjp-rule-law-index/>
17. World Bank (2025). *Foreign direct investment, net inflows (%of GDP) World Bank Open Data - Data set*. World Development Indicators. Retrieved 05/05/2025 from <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/BX.KLT.DINV.GD.ZS>